

Traditional and electronic environmental media and its role in spreading environmental awareness (the role of the media in developing environmental awareness).

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ABSTRACT

In this research paper, we try to address the issue of environmental media, by clarifying the relationship between the media organization and preserving the environment by clarifying the environmental media message in an effective way, as environmental media remains an integral part of the economic industry, as the media and the economy are in a multi-faceted and lasting partnership. Able to persuade members of society to adopt positive environmental behaviors that would achieve the goals of sustainable development.

In this study, we touched upon three main elements through which we tried to study environmental media in all its aspects, whether the conceptual framework of environmental information, in addition to the role of environmental media in spreading environmental awareness, and the third element dealt with the obstacles and challenges facing the achievement of environmental media goals. Also, at the end of the study, we reached a set of findings and recommendations.

1. Introduction

Societies today suffer from many environmental problems that have become directly or indirectly affecting human life, and if natural environmental problems cannot be avoided by a person because they are outside his scope, then other environmental problems are usually the person who is the main cause of them through his daily practices. The issue of environmental pollution is one of the important topics that arouse interest in the current era, as this phenomenon is classified among environmental crimes and its seriousness is embodied in many indicators that directly affect human life and endanger him. Perhaps what makes this more severe is its lack of recognition of the borders between countries, and that it took It is increasing in a turbulent manner on society, in addition to the fact that it is no longer possible to hide its negative effects on human health and social life, as this phenomenon can be compared sociologically within the framework of social problems, which is the deviation from the rules and standards set by society to determine the right and correct behavior. The imbalance in the basic components of the environment such as water, air, and soil, and every change that affects the original values of societies represents the essence of the problem of environmental pollution and is primarily a result of deviation in practices. Humanity and its departure from the general framework of environmental protection rules.

The need of societies in general and development in particular to environmental media increases day after day, and this need is urgent, continuous and renewed, and becomes more urgent when an environmental problem such as pollution, the spread of epidemics and agricultural pests, and the pollution of the seas by leaking oils, petroleum and chemicals, the presence of environmental media, contrary to what most believe People, going beyond issues related to waste, sewage, and random construction to all areas of life, primarily aimed at achieving development.

As the issues of media, the environment and the economy are intertwined and interconnected, therefore, pollution problems have become one of the priorities and concerns of the media and public opinion in particular in industrially

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advanced societies. As a result, the entire media specialization in newspapers and television channels and the opening of electronic pages on social media sites, where environmental media leads an important and decisive role in a changing world, and the issue of forming environmental awareness regarding waste remains the responsibility of the media, because of its profound impact on the groups of society, regardless of its different social structure, cultural composition, economic conditions and the nature of its political system. The media cannot undertake this role without participatory action that includes all highly civil society, as well as non-governmental organizations, educational and cultural institutions, where media policies can achieve sustainable comprehensive development by incorporating the principle of information and communication in development plans and giving them an important role by educating members of society about the importance of community service, and the importance of volunteer work as a social value and public awareness of preserving environmental protection and rationalization of the use of water, energy and clean products.

The emergence of the so-called environmental or green media as an important field came in response to achieving the requirements of comprehensive development, in which the environmental aspect and environmental awareness are among its most important pillars. The necessity of forming environmental awareness is a prerequisite for achieving sustainable development. Harmony and interdependence between the environment and its safety and social and economic development that are indispensable in all development projects and programs, and in order to raise the levels of environmental awareness, the appropriate media must be monitored to bring about change.

2. What is environmental media:

2.1 Defining environmental media

The media is the objective expression of the mentality of the masses, their spirit, their tendencies and trends at the same time, as expressed by "Outjour", and this requires that the media have three basic characteristics: seriousness and modernity, importance and magnitude, accuracy and objectivity (Ali Ajwa, 2004, p. 12).

As for specialized media, it is media that aims to transmit information to the public about a specific field of knowledge with the aim of enlightening the public and making it aware of what is happening in this specialized field of knowledge. Specialized media science emerged in response to the various aspirations and desires of the public, where the concerns of the masses were divided into specialized media disciplines. To satisfy these special media requirements.

Among the forms of specialized media are sports media, political media, tourism media ... etc., but the actual emergence of the term environmental media is one with the frequent development in definition, concept and use since the seventies of the last century, after it was a transfer of environmental news and press excitement for more sales, it became his Policies, plans, and functions to achieve various goals, just as the media has a role in talking "development media" in helping people form a correct opinion of the content of reality, environmental media has become a tool that works to clarify environmental concepts by surrounding the audience and target of the message and the environmental media material with all the facts and correct objective information In a way that contributes to rooting sustainable environmental development. (Sanaa Muhammad Al-Jabour, , 2011, p. 12).

Environmental media is a specialized media that directs its message and employs it in the service of environmental issues, using many means and communication channels to reach the public, and the need for it has increased in recent times in conjunction with the growing international interest in the environment, and the emergence of many environmental problems in many countries of the world. Talking about environmental media, we cannot overlook a fundamental point represented in environmental awareness, which is one of the most essential components that direct positive environmental behavior for an individual or even institutions as moral entities or legal personalities. Awareness is the turning point for bringing about change in protecting the environment. On it, environmental media is to create environmental awareness and motivate it to actively participate in development and environmental projects to preserve the rights of future generations and to live in a healthy and sound environment.

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point represented in environmental awareness, which is one of the most essential components that direct positive environmental behavior for the individual or even institutions as moral entities or legal personalities. Awareness is the turning point to bring about change in protecting the environment, so the most important goal is to focus on Environmental media is the formation of environmental awareness and motivation to actively participate in development and environmental projects to preserve future generations and live in a healthy and safe environment.(Muhammad Qirat, p3).

The World Bank is defined as the transfer of environmental information in order to enrich the public's knowledge and influence its opinions and behaviors towards the environment. "It refers to the informational material in the media, which deals with environmental issues, causes, dimensions, and solutions for treatment, aiming to influence and educate the public and modify its behavior towards protecting the environment" .(Radwan Salaman 2012, p99).

2.2 Concept of environmental awareness:

Environmental awareness is the individual's awareness of the requirements of the environment and the development of his correct behaviors towards the environment, and this is through introducing him to the components of the environment and the relationship that binds these components together, and knowing the problems resulting from disturbing their balance, and ways to solve these problems to return to the box of a sound environmental balance, and environmental awareness is not It is an innate matter for many people, but it is learned behaviors that can be instilled in them and modified their behavior towards the environment. (environmental awareness).

Environmental awareness is "citizens' awareness of the environment and the problems related to it, providing them with knowledge, skills and trends, and taking individual and collective responsibility towards solving contemporary problems and working to prevent new environmental problems. (Mujahid Muhammad Ragheb, 2006, p 68).

That is, the process of preparing the human being a successful interaction with his natural environment, including the various resources it includes, and this process requires working on developing certain aspects of the learner, including clarifying concepts and deepening the principles necessary to understand the interrelationships between the human being and his culture on the one hand and the biophysical environment around him on the other hand. It also requires the development of skills that enable a person to contribute to solving the problems that his environment may encounter and the dangers that threaten it, and to contribute to the development of the conditions of this environment as well as the formation of the trends and values that govern human behavior, the effects of his tendencies and interests towards his environment and the appreciation of the importance of working on its maintenance And preserving it, "the environmental awareness is the individual's awareness of his role in facing the environment". (William illston, 1974, p24).

Environmental media: Environmental media is a device that can instill a love for the environment among members of society and raise issues of concern to them. It also works on the interpretation, understanding and awareness of the recipient of contemporary environmental issues, as the emergence of environmental media has been associated with the problem of the risks of economic development and its impact on the environment in which a person lives and in front of Hole Environmental disasters The environmental media had an active role in shedding light on these environmental crimes. (Muhammad Abu Samra 2009, p 39-40).

The first appearance of the term environmental media dates back to the seventies of the last century, and it began to develop with the holding of conferences. After it was a carrier of news and press excitement, it had policies, plans and functions to achieve various goals. (Arab Organization for Education, 1990, p 156).

Environmental media is defined as "a type of specialized media that aims to convey information to the public about a specific field of knowledge that aims to enlighten public opinion and make it aware of what is happening in this specialized field of knowledge," and it is concerned with environmental affairs that have a relationship to the economy and looks forward to achieving sustainable development that called for Ms. Grohalim Bruntand, Prime Minister of Norway, in her 1987 report "Our Common Future".

Environmental media is a specialized media that directs its message and employs it in the service of environmental issues, using many means and communication channels to reach the public and the need for it has increased in recent times in conjunction with the growing international interest in the environment and the emergence of many environmental problems due to the continuous development of the economy. (Jihan Rashti, , 1978, p 161).

Environmental media is a complex expression of media and the environment, and media is considered one of the basic ingredients in preserving the environment, which includes all areas of life.

Environmental media is the process of creating and disseminating scientific facts related to the environment, through the mass media, with the aim of creating a degree of environmental awareness, leading to sustainable development . (Mary Soliman, 1998, p 37).

Environmental media is a tool that works to clarify environmental concepts by informing the recipient and target audience of the environmental media message with sufficient facts and objective information, in a way that contributes to postponing the development of the sustainable environment, and enlightening the target audience with a good opinion on the environmental issues and problems at hand. (Taher Muna, Hamza Barghi,1987, p 54) .It is concerned with environmental issues, and deals with them with analysis, interpretation and explanation, with the aim of spreading environmental awareness among members of society.

2.3 The difference between traditional and electronic environmental media:

The concept of electronic environmental media

Electronic environmental media can be defined as a new type of media that shares the concept with traditional media, general principles and goals, and is done through electronic methods, foremost of which is the Internet. (Marwa Essam Salah, *Electronic* , 2015, p 148).What distinguishes electronic media from traditional media is its dependence on a new means of modern media, which is the combination of all Traditional means of communication aims to deliver the required contents in distinct and effective forms in larger ways. (Qinan Abdullah Al-Ghamdi, 2012, p7).

It is an expression of a new type of new environmental media that shares the traditional concept of media in the classic means of communication in the concept, general principles, and objectives and differs from it in that it depends on a new communication medium, which is the Internet. This new medium allows for the merging of both traditional means of communication in order to communicate The environmental content to the target audience, via the network, in differentiated and influential forms in a more compelling way, due to the availability of an interactive feature that is often absent within the framework of the traditional environmental communication model that is one-way. The Internet, as a new media channel, allows the presentation of environmental content and communication messages in a digital electronic way through the international information network, without resorting to broadcast stations or printers, and in ways that combine text, image and sound, and at the same time breaks down the barrier between the sender and the recipient so that the recipient can respond directly, and he can To interact with the environmental messages and contents he receives either with the site administration or with other recipients who share environmental concern, so that this environmental electronic communication process is limited to using the Internet specifically.

- The main difference between environmental media in its traditional form through classic media, and electronic environmental media through new media using Internet applications, is the difference only in the use of the communication channel or communication medium, so the difference between traditional media and new media is interactive and the media The multiplicity and superiority of the new media in addition to the features of asynchrony, and many additional advantages that make there a clear difference in the methods of awareness, as the message is the medium, according to McLuhan, the author of the theory of technological determinism. (Mehri Shafika, 2016, p 204).

Among the differences between traditional environmental media and electronic environmental media, we find:

- The sources of environmental information are monopolized in the traditional means of communication. However, the sources on the Internet are not monopolized and free. They are characterized by the multiplicity of gatekeepers. They may in themselves be a source for traditional media in the field of environment.

- The various actors in the traditional environmental media are official bodies to protect the environment, environmental disasters, and industry ... However, the actors in electronic environmental media are industrial and service institutions of all kinds, individuals of various groups, segments, social statuses and the economy (youth, women, children), Civil society organizations such as environmental associations, political parties active in the field of the environment, researchers and specialists in environmental sciences, environmental writers and bloggers.

2.4 Components of environmental awareness:

Environmental awareness in its origin consists of three separate intervening rings at the same time, namely:

Environmental education and education: It starts with education from kindergarten and continues through general education stages to university education with a basic condition, and there is an integration of the objectives of educational and educational programs, and environmental education is intended to find competencies and political, economic, technical and scientific competencies capable of dealing with various environmental problems through different scientific methods. And, like any educational curriculum, it has its own policy in terms of preparing different levels, and developing programs and curricula. (Zuhair Abd al-Latif, 2014, p24).

Environmental culture: It starts from providing information sources such as books and publications by environmental educators in the broadcasted and published discussions and debates, and in accidents, calamities, and environmental issues of direct relevance to society, especially those with media output.

- **Environmental media:** It is one of the most important wings of environmental awareness, and it is a tool that, if properly invested, would have a positive impact to raise environmental awareness and spread a sound awareness of environmental issues, and environmental media works in the interpretation, understanding and awareness of the recipient of contemporary environmental issues and building certain convictions towards the environment and its issues. (Sanaa Muhammad Al-Jabour, 2011, p 40).

2.5 Characteristics of environmental awareness:

Environmental awareness has certain characteristics that can be summarized in the following points:

- The formation and development of environmental awareness does not necessarily require raising a systemic environment, because the environment surrounding the individual has an effective effect on that.

- Environmental awareness includes the convergence of two aspects of the cognitive aspect and the emotional aspect. Although environmental awareness is related to the emotional aspect, it is saturated with different cognitive aspects.

- Environmental awareness does not include positive behavior towards the environment in all circumstances, as there are many individuals fully aware of environmental dangers and problems, but they do not take positive behaviors towards them;

Environmental awareness is the first step in forming environmental trends that control an individual's behavior;

Environmental awareness is a predictive function of what may be produced by the individual's behavior towards the environment in the future.

By integrating the environmental education systems, environmental education, culture and environmental information, the public can be reached to a reasonable degree of the required environmental awareness, according to various and thoughtful gradual media plans and strategies, and this is one of the tasks of environmental media. (Samir Mahmoud, , 2008, p. 148).

3. The role of environmental media in spreading environmental awareness

3.1 Environmental media and its role in creating environmental awareness

The ecosystem is based on the balance between its components, so if one or more of its components are affected, the rest of the components are affected and the relationship between them is changed, and it becomes unable to maintain its previous equilibrium, so a so-called "ecosystem imbalance" occurs, and thus problems appear Environmental such as forest fires, harmful radiation, a significant increase in population, desertification, ozone depletion, pollution of air, water and soil, waste. (Karam Ali Hafez, , 2017, p 16).

These environmental problems, whether their origin is natural (as a result of changing natural conditions such as heat and rain, which leads to fires or the migration of living organisms and their extinction), or their origin is abnormal (resulting from human activities of the human being), so their treatment and attempt to address them is done before everything through Providing information to individuals regarding proper behaviors that prevent disruption of this ecosystem. Hence, media of all kinds, traditional and modern, are one of the most important means that enable this to be achieved.

As a result of pollution problems and environmental disasters that occurred in the seventies, the Environment Conference in Stockholm in 1972 came, and as a result of these environmental problems that occurred in that period, such as the crash of the oil tanker Amokkandis in 1978 and the Soviet nuclear reactor accident, Nobel notes in 1986, the interest of various media outlets intensified about issues. Environment, and this is how environmental media began to appear, and environmental media is concerned with issues and topics related to nature and the environment, and their reflection on the overall health, economic, scientific and cultural, heritage of human beings ... and it is a link between the sciences related to the environment and the public. (Mustafa Darwish, 2003).

The first origins of the media's interest in the environment go back to the year 1870 in the city of "Minisota." In 1920, Holoch founded a magazine that dealt with environmental issues. The interest in the environment and environmental media in the Arab world began after the "Rio" conference for the environment in 1922, and this interest was reflected. With regard to the amount of attention paid by Arab media to environmental issues, and with regard to media coverage, the results indicate that the volume of media coverage of the environment has grown significantly, rising to a percentage of 100% in small newspapers, and the number of news stories has tripled between the years 1987-1990. Articles dealing with environmental issues increased from 200 articles in 1960 to 1600 in 1970 (Free Badis, , 2017, p 367-382).

Environmental media is considered important and fundamental to creating an environmental awareness by exploiting the media in increasing societal awareness of environmental problems and reaching environmental rationalization in human interaction with his surroundings until he reaches to play an important role in early warning by monitoring any environmental defect that occurs and directing public opinion until It is one of the crucial issues that can have its own legislation and laws that regulate it until it becomes part of its daily life. (Ali Abdel-Fattah, , 2016, p 4).

Environmental media aims to develop environmental awareness among the various sectors of society in order to actively participate in the development, monitoring and review of environmental policies, and it also prepares the public and officials to support the implementation of environmental policies and measures. (Karam Ali Hafez,2017, p3).

In fact, the specialized environmental media differs from the environmental news that is covered in the media, as it is supposed to allocate a permanent media space in the media of all kinds to display environmental problems and challenges and contribute to solving them, at least on the awareness level, and specialists must also supervise Environmentalists based on the content of what is published to ensure that the information is technically and environmentally correct. (The Lebanese Ministry of Environment 2017).

3.2 The role of environmental media can be summarized in the following points:

Disseminating environmental awareness through print, audio and visual media.

Forming a new culture aimed at achieving a better environment;

The production of specialized programs and documentary television works on protecting the environment from the dangers of various climate and environmental changes.

- Presenting educational programs and various awareness programs on television and places where the masses and youth gather;

Building environmental awareness at a wide audience level through targeted programs and series.

TV advertising as one of the effective tools in dealing with the issue of the environment. (Mehri Shafika,2016, p206).

- The environmental media mainly aims to achieve environmental awareness and education in the field of the environment.

The media, especially the traditional media, contribute through media forms (news, report, investigation, series ...) to the process of environmental education and the formation of an environmentally conscious generation that seeks to preserve it.

"As the environmental media seek to achieve the greatest impact on the target audience, to reach the largest possible geographical area, and to bring about change, direction and the desired education among those who are in it ...

Based on that, those in charge of environmental media conduct accurate and in-depth studies to know the distinct content of media messages. (Zuhair Abd al-Latif Abed, Ahmad al-Abed Abu al-Saeed, , 2018, p79).

Some research indicates that environmental associations see the press as the most important means of influencing public opinion and government institutions in favor of environmental issues (Free Badis, 2017, p369).

3.3 The role and methods of environmental media in spreading environmental awareness:

Perhaps the important role of environmental media is to spread environmental culture, advancement and environmental awareness through various print, audio and visual media, in order to protect the environment and to search for ways to reduce its current problems, because a person who does not know his environment will destroy it and thus he will destroy himself, without knowing. Here comes the role of environmental media in educating this person about the damages to his environment, and his awareness of how to confront and reduce them, and also to educate him about the best way to deal with his environment, preserving it and even improving it.

The media has an important mission, which is to raise public interest in environmental crimes and formulate an opinion capable of confronting them, as the media is one of the educational institutions most capable of spreading environmental awareness among members of society. (Ali Abdel-Fattah Kanaan, 2014, p 85).

Environmental media methods for achieving environmental awareness:

Implementing specialized lectures, seminars, seminars, conferences and workshops to spread awareness and increase education on various environmental issues.

- Implementing radio and television programs that reveal the environmental realities of the citizen and enlighten him about his role and responsibilities towards environmental problems.

Harnessing the press to spread environmental awareness through its articles, investigations, cartoons and other methods;

Encouraging individuals to visit museums, galleries, zoos and nature reserves, which are important sources of environmental information for people of all groups, provided that these visits will develop in people the positive attitudes towards the environment.

Encouraging individuals to form and engage in clubs, societies and civil organizations with environmental goals. Highlighting its objectives and activities, supporting its programs, and working on the success of its projects in preserving the environment - the success of health and family awareness programs and public education programs implemented by various government institutions such as the ministries of education, higher education, health, agriculture, energy, social development, tourism, water and others.

Guidance for program writers, writers, performances and films with light information on the environment. (Ratib Al-Saud, 2007, p 257).

3.4 Contribution of Environmental Media to Environmental Protection:

Environmental media is considered one of the most important main actors in protecting the natural and industrial environment, especially with the increase in environmental problems on the one hand, and on the other hand, the access of this media to most people's homes, and therefore one of its most important goals was to create real environmental education that would be the cornerstone of protecting the ecosystem with all its implications in the absence of any obstacle preventing the media in general from playing its legally assigned role.

▪ The role of environmental media in creating environmental education:

As for the seriousness of the environmental situation or dilemma, as some describe it, the international community has realized the necessity of preserving the environment and limiting environmental degradation, although this realization came somewhat late. Article 54 gives the authority to control audiovisual media the right to monitor the media and

accompany them in the constant vigil of protecting the environment, promoting environmental culture, and preserving the health of the population. (Law 04/14 of 02/24/2014).

The definitions of the concept of environmental education varied, but all refer to it as the process of forming values, attitudes, skills and perceptions necessary for the learner, in order to understand and appreciate the complex relationships that link humans with the biosphere. It illustrates the imperative of preserving the environment and the need to properly exploit the interests of mankind in order to preserve his life and raise his living standards. (Hamid Hamlawi, fame tape 2017, p1902).

In order for the environmental media to achieve its role in the successful impact on the state's environmental policy, an integrated campaign must be prepared to address any environmental problem that is of importance to the state and has a direct link to the public, and before starting this media campaign, those responsible for this campaign must be convinced of the importance of this problem and its impact on community development. (Abdul Rahman Abdullah Al-Awadi, 1993, p19). The goal of primary environmental education is to reach what is known as environmental awareness, which is based on the individual's awareness of the environment's requirements through his sense and knowledge of its components, the relationships between them, as well as environmental issues and how to deal with them. (Zain Meloy, 2013, p. 3).

Many environmental laws have also indicated important points that the media should be one of the main actors in the stage of environmental education. To try to instill in the public the citizens through direct contact with them, through television programs, radio sessions, specialized awareness and awareness campaigns, or through other media of the private or public sector, whether magazines or channels, by planting some environmental values . (The Scientific Symposium on Environmental Education, 1975) , For example : (Bafzal Muhammad,2020, p 75).

Banning all publicity in green spaces.

Prohibition of building without a permit or without respecting the plans .

- Prohibiting the use of dispatched products that are likely to pose a danger to persons in the manufacture of envelopes intended to contain direct foodstuffs or in the manufacture of things intended for children.

Protection, valuation and rational use of heritage, natural and cultural resources and preserving them for future generations.

The quality of the bathing water is subjected to periodic analyzes, and users must be informed of the results of the tests periodically.

Businesses to promote the research, development and use of renewable energies benefit from the incentives under Finance Law.

Sensitization of the importance of mountain areas and the need to protect and upgrade them in the context of sustainable development.

Everyone has the right to use water resources within the limits of public benefit and to respect legal obligations.

▪ **The role of the media in developing environmental awareness:**

The media play a central role in shaping environmental awareness among the general public through the text of Laws 03-10, whether in the field of providing it with complete and correct information on environmental issues, or in shaping trends and attitudes towards these issues and also in defining environmental priorities at all local, regional and international levels. Where environmental awareness is the first step in forming environmental trends that control an individual's behavior.

Environmental media is considered one of the most important wings of environmental awareness, and it is a tool that, if properly invested, would have a positive impact to raise environmental awareness and spread a sound awareness of environmental issues. Environmental media works in the interpretation, understanding and awareness of the recipient of contemporary environmental issues. (Article 3 of Law 10-03, 2003).

- **Environmental media and civil society awareness-raising activities to highlight the role of the circular economy:**

The importance of awareness-raising activities carried out by civil society organizations doubles with the proliferation of environmental problems, which have become a real threat to the environment in all its elements, and the role of civil society mainly includes spreading awareness through environmental education by presenting its content and sensitizing the importance of the danger of widespread waste, where the circular economy is adopted. On reducing society's dependence on scarce natural resources by making maximum use of available resources and reusing them. (Ardouan Salaman, 2006, p189).

In view of the risks to the environment due to the industrialization process on the one hand and the problem of increasing the volume of waste on the other hand, as this resulted in negative impacts on the environment, the more individuals deplete natural resources, the greater their footprint on the earth. (Saeedan Ali, 2015, p130).

3.4 The effectiveness of environmental media in raising civil society awareness of the requirements of the circular economy

Article 3 of Law 10-03 related to the environment and sustainable development stipulated the principle of participation, which includes the decisions of the participation of those concerned directly or indirectly to make decisions related to environmental protection (Sanaa Mohamed Jabbour, 2006, p. 189), which are all mechanisms that enhance the status of environmental awareness among members of Algerian civil society, to reduce pollutants within institutions and control. It must work to reduce it and create a new culture aimed at achieving a better environment. Environmental media also plays a rationalizing role to get rid of garbage and waste in human behavior by relying on the circular economy and reducing the environmental footprint.

Environmental media is considered the most influential means in changing the individual and society's attitudes towards issues related to the circular economy, and thus the individual contributes to how to deal with his environment and make this awareness his behavior, as his role remains to spread environmental culture and promote environmental awareness through multiple media means to achieve the requirements of the circular economy and achieve Sustainable Development. (Yusef Emad Sharaf al-Din, 2003, p. 128).

Environmental media also plays a prominent role in dealing with disasters, crises, wars and accidents, (Ahmad Ismail Al-Bawab, p 96), especially at a time of disasters caused by industry and the development of the economy, and its important role lies in informing people about what is happening and in directing their behavior to interact and deal with dangers, psychologically or socially and scientifically, which mitigates the effects of the disaster. And limits their aggravation, hence the environmental media dimension in managing and directing the economy towards promising future horizons, and scientific studies confirm the role of environmental media in economic activity through the following elements. (Adel Sadiq Muhammad, p18).

-Environmental media is carried out by environmental media in relation to the creation and presentation of information and the reduction of anxiety in economic activities.

- Environmental media is a major effective tool and one of the tools of the crisis, both internally and externally;

Environmental media achieves successful economic growth without pollution and waste of damage to the environment and people;

- The contribution of radio and television programs and the written press specialized in environmental media in uncovering environmental facts and guiding the citizen to his role and responsibilities towards environmental problems.

4. Obstacles and challenges facing achieving the objectives of environmental media

4.1 Obstacles to achieving environmental security in the media

One of the biggest obstacles is; When environmental media becomes mere media reports devoid of spirit, most of the time the information broadcast or published by the media is shaded, distorted or interpreted in an unproductive way. The media in countries, especially underdeveloped countries, often hide facts related to environmental problems and

disasters, under the pretext of not raising the public against them, and information related to these issues is not accessible to individuals and is difficult for them to perceive and understand.

It is also noticed the absence of procedural regulatory texts explaining how to exercise the right to environmental media, although Law 10-03 includes it and referred its applications to regulation, as Article 7, paragraph 3 of it stipulates, "specifying the modalities for communicating this information through regulation." Article 9, paragraph 3 of the same The law on the special right to information "specifies the conditions of this right, as well as the methods for informing citizens of protection measures through regulation." Unless these texts are issued, the implementation of this right is impossible. On the one hand, and on the other hand, it is noticed the reluctance of those claiming this right because of the lack of sufficient information among the citizens about the way the administration works, as a result of the great shortage of media devoted to the environment in the face of environmental hazards.

What is noticed in this context is the lack of interest of the administration in the rules of publishing and media or the opinions of citizens, as it has settled in the collective thought that the administration does not resort to informing them until after it has decided its position towards the issue before it if it is raised, in addition to what the media suffers in reporting and covering environmental news As we find that most of the environmental scientific topics covered by the media in most of the third world countries are transmitted by strange scientific means without referring to the original sources to investigate local views and various field information. (Naguib Saab, 2006, p46).

Numerous studies and research have also indicated a set of obstacles and challenges that may limit the effective and positive countries of ecological information in the field of achieving environmental security, which is based on combating pollution and preventing the unlimited depletion of natural resources, and among these obstacles:

- Failure to support, encourage and intensify awareness-raising programs that clarify and attract community members to the importance of environmental security;
- The lack of a clear and specific methodology in the awareness programs on environmental security;
- Not giving the issue of environmental pollution and achieving environmental security the importance it deserves;
- Media professionals are not enrolled in advanced training courses in the field of environmental protection;
- The media does not focus on the issue of the environment sufficiently.
- The lack of compatibility of awareness-raising programs on the environment with all segments of society;

Insufficient information to build a strong environmental media system;

Not benefiting from the expertise of media professionals from developed countries.

- The lack of clear cooperation between the agencies concerned with the environment and the media. (Abdul Aziz Abdullah Ahmad Al-Shaya, 2003, p 156).

4.2 The obstacles facing the media in contributing to environmental awareness:

4.2.1. Lack of media interest in the environment:

In fact, environmental media does not give environmental issues the attention they need, and this is exemplified by the lack of press spaces dedicated to this, the small number of radio and television programs, with their limited time space and the lack of use of specialists in environmental affairs and issues, as well as the scarcity of websites interested in environmental issues, As well as the limited number of satellite stations and specialized newspapers concerned with environmental affairs in general.

4.2.2. The absence of professionalism in addressing media professionals

This is clearly evidenced by the fact that the relationship between media professionals and environmental information sources is not subject to professional considerations insofar as it is subject to considerations of common or mutual interests, not to mention that it is affected by pressure groups from industry and business in some cases far from environmental laws and considerations.

4.2.3. Officials are not convinced of the viability of the environment and its issues

It is unfortunate that some of those in charge of the various media do not have real visions and convictions in the viability of environmental affairs and its importance to the masses, so often the environmental page or the space allocated to it is sacrificed in exchange for publishing any other press material of any type, and the publication or display of the space is canceled or postponed. Environmental Comparison between a paid advertisement that provides a financial resource for a media outlet, or an environmental program that media leaders are not convinced of its usefulness in the first place.

4.2.4. The media's reluctance to work in the field of environmental media

This issue is one of the important issues that negatively affect environmental media. The real reasons for the reluctance of media professionals to work in the field of environmental media can be accomplished in the following points:

- Specialization in environmental sciences is new within the many environmental disciplines, and dealing with an issue requires a varied scientific familiarity, because environmental issues have intertwined dimensions with economics, development, sociology, politics, biological and plant sciences, etc., and because most journalists lack a scientific culture, so they turn away from work in the field of environmental media. ;
- The time required to write an environmental press report takes longer, to review some technical, scientific and statistical matters, which makes the media journalist less productive, that is, with little access to financial income.
- The nature of the environmental problem does not constitute a scoop in the traditional concept of journalism, unless it is related to an environmental disaster or to severe damages resulting from pollution. Therefore, the traditional journalist cannot conduct dialogues about the environment and its problems.

Non-encouragement of those in charge of media organizations and pushing them to delve into the field of the environment, and the promise of allocating pages in newspapers or programs on radio and television that are concerned with environmental affairs and environmental awareness, the lack of specialized archives and the television library, and the low wages that he grants for topics and reporting that need effort and money Two big. (Hussein Ahmed Shehata, Mohamed Hassan Awad, 2013).

4.3 the factors that affect the form and type of media treatment of environmental issues :

- the official state media policy and the state's general environmental policy;
- The level and type of environmental awareness prevailing among the general public, leaders, decision makers and those in the communication process
- General Environmental Education .
- The media treatment of environmental issues contains a set of variables, as follows:
- The goal of treatment is to set priorities for treatment;
- Categories of the target audience: the ruling elite, the strategic elite, the general public;
- Choosing the method according to the topic and the issue raised with the complementarity of roles between this medium;
- Influencing the communicator by developing his level of awareness and awareness of the environment.
- The role of the mass media is an important component in the system of continuous education, education and training in providing the individual with an environmental awareness that enables him to perform his role in assisting various social groups according to the following aspects and dimensions:
- Facilitating environmental knowledge and uncovering facts related to environmental problems;
- Forming positive trends towards the environment, that is, taking the necessary attitudes towards it in terms of sensing its problems and showing willingness to contribute to solving them;

-Positive participation in adopting behaviors that reduce risks to the environment and stimulate participation in volunteer work;

-The most important thing is to adopt a vision based on a sense of shared responsibility between the public and official authorities, and to correct some of the deficient statements and perceptions in dealing with environmental issues. (Robert Logan A, 1992, p107).

5. Conclusion:

In the conclusion of this research paper, what we emphasize through the results we have reached in this study is that environmental media is an effective tool in achieving sustainable development, through several methods, whether it is traditional or electronic environmental media through social networks, especially if It has been used to serve areas specialized in sustainable development, as the environment and environmental awareness are the first pillars to achieve sustainable development.

As caring for the environment and maintaining its balance is preserving the human being, because the imbalance of the ecosystem's balance leads to negative effects on it, threatening it economically and socially by affecting the wealth on the earth, and affecting it in terms of health, which causes him various diseases, from here it became awareness Community members through various means, including traditional and new media, one of the most important mechanisms necessary today.

Results:

- The growing interest in the issue of the environment on the part of environmental activists through social networking sites, Facebook, which is considered an important means for environmental activists;

-Environmental media is an important means of accompanying the circular economy and directing it in order to achieve sustainable development.

- Through environmental media, the citizen is fully aware of what is happening and provides consistent and correct information;

-Environmental media as a strategic media field that is still in its genetic stage suffers from the absence of an environmental media strategy;

- Environmental media is an effective contributor to uncovering facts for the citizen and the various partners as an effective means of awareness work;

- Little and no training opportunities for journalists working in environmental media;

-The circular economy is the best alternative to a linear economy, and it contributes widely to environmental protection and sustainable development.

-Environmental media is specialized media attached to reality and the concerns of citizens and business owners.

- The reason for the users' lack of interest in environmental awareness issues is due to the weak environmental socialization;

- Despite the importance of environmental media, which is considered a transformative tool in the economy and sustainable development, it is still confined to forums and round tables.

- Weak economic culture among workers in the environmental media, and their lack of motivation to develop their knowledge;

-The circular economy is a dynamic economy that attracts new sources of income and aims to change the way we live in industry and consumption;

- Media officials' lack of interest in environmental media;

- A number of prominent figures in environmental media have turned to offices and left field work, and some of them have completely abandoned the profession for other work due to lack of incentives.

-For those in charge of the environmental media process through Facebook, they are specialists in the fields of environment and ecology.

Recommendations:

- Establishing adequate incentives and paying attention to media professionals active in the field of environmental and economic media;

-Encouraging research and scientific exchange in the field of environmental media and the circular economy;

-The necessity of training journalists specializing in the environmental and economic fields;

- Enacting new laws in line with investment in the circular economy;

-Holding educational forums and seminars focusing on the importance of environmental media and the circular economy.

- Developing the capabilities of journalists through missions, training courses and workshops, and attracting qualified people with knowledge and extensive experience;

- Launching radio and television programs concerned with economics, sustainable development and environmental media, while opening the way for audiovisuals by --launching private and public channels concerned with markets, economy and development;

-The need to promote the general environmental awareness of individuals, which is still below the required level and below the desired goal;

- Directing the consumption pattern to recycled products and adopting a circular economy policy;

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